

Nitrofluorene-Based A–D–A Electron Acceptors for Organic Photovoltaics[†]

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We explored nitrofluorene derivatives as tunable electron-withdrawing groups for acceptor-donor-acceptor (A–D–A) type non-fullerene acceptors. Their optoelectronic properties and performance in bulk heterojunction solar cells with PBDB-T donor polymer are reported. Introducing up to four nitro groups to the fluorene unit results in deeper frontier orbital levels and reduced HOMO-LUMO gap and red-shifted absorption bands. Optimal device performance was achieved for trinitrofluorene acceptors with a solubilizing ester group in the trade-off between decreased voltage and increased photocurrent. 2D brickwork packing found by single crystal X-ray analysis of tetranitrofluorene derivative is different from the interpenetrating 3D network found for high-efficiency A–D–A acceptors and might be the reason for the poor charge transport properties. Steric hindrance between benzothiadiazole and nitrofluorene units can be relieved by the use of furan linkers, which planarize the conjugated backbone but decreased solubility.

Introduction

Over the last decade, organic photovoltaics (OPVs) have seen tremendous advances toward the goal of offering clean, renewable and inexpensive energy source.^{1,2,3,4} Beside the development of conjugated polymers,^{5,6,7} a significant part of the progress arises from the refined molecular design of non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs), which enjoys the benefit of structural diversity and enhanced

[†] Electronic Supporting Information (ESI) available: General methods, X-ray crystallography, synthesis of intermediates, redox potentials for cyclic voltammetry, SCLC measurements, AFM images for blend films, NMR spectra of the NFAs and intermediates.

optical absorption over their fullerene predecessors.^{8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13} In particular, acceptor-donor-acceptor (A–D–A) architecture has recently attracted great interest.^{14,15} Its success in OPV devices is attributed to the strong quadruple interaction leading to efficient π - π stacking and a special three-dimensional interpenetrating network enabling isotropic charge transport.^{16,17,18} With the introduction of new A–D–A type materials including the IT-series^{19, 20, 21} and Y-series,^{22,23,24,25} a power conversion efficiency (PCE) above 18% has been achieved with single-junction devices, opening up the door for the commercial application of OPV technology.

Currently, several acceptor end-groups have been incorporated in A–D–A molecules, including cyanoacetate,²⁶ malononitrile,^{27,28} rhodanine derivatives,^{29,30,31} 1,1-dicyanomethylene-3-indanone (INCN) or its analogs,^{19,32,33} barbiturate^{34,35} and acenaphthenone derivatives.³⁶ Most of these building blocks employed cyano (CN) groups as the main electron-withdrawing functionality. Halogen atoms including fluorine²⁰ and chlorine,²¹ and occasionally trifluoromethyl groups^{37,38} were also used to further enhance the acceptor strength. However, relatively little attention has been paid to nitro (NO₂) groups,³⁹ despite being one of the strongest electron-withdrawing groups (Hammett constants σ_p/σ_m for NO₂ and CN substituents are 0.78/0.71 and 0.66/0.56, respectively).⁴⁰ Nitrobenzene was once incorporated in the NFA backbone in light of its simplicity and achieved a PCE of ~2%.⁴¹ Only recently, nitro-based end-groups have been incorporated into the A–D–A architecture and achieved reasonable performance although the success is largely built on top of the already well-developed INCN acceptor.⁴² Featuring an extended conjugation and efficient π -stacking, nitrofluorene derivatives were used in the fabrication of supramolecular liquid crystals to enhance charge carrier mobility.⁴³ This old yet largely overlooked class of electron acceptors offers excellent synthetic flexibility enabling fine-tuning of electron affinity, intramolecular charge transfer (ICT, when combined with electron-donating moieties) and crystallization behavior.^{44,45,46} Our recent work showed the promise of nitrofluorenones as semiconductors⁴⁷ or dopants⁴⁸ for organic field-effect transistors (OFETs). These results motivated us to further explore nitrofluorenes in the design of A–D–A acceptors for OPV applications.

Herein, we report the synthesis, electronic structure and OPV device performance of a new series of NFAs combining nitrofluorene electron-withdrawing termini and the classical indacenodithiophenebis(benzothiadiazole) (IDTB) core,⁴⁹ and compare their electronic properties to those of rhodanine-based NFAs. The nitrofluorene NFAs show a broad absorption band extending to the near-infrared (NIR) region. This band is red-shifted with more nitro groups,

resulting in optical band-gaps (E_g) as low as 1.25 eV in the solid state. The large steric size of fluorene termini comparing to rhodanine (and most other termini used in NFAs) causes a significant twist of the molecule which can be mitigated by the incorporation of furan linkers. The photovoltaic efficiency, tested in bulk heterojunction (BHJ) devices with the common PBDB-T donor polymer, is limited by low solubility and electron mobility of fluorene-based NFAs. These problems can be partially mitigated with solubilizing alkoxy carbonyl substituents and planarization of the NFA backbone using furan linker.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis

All the NFAs were synthesized by Knoevenagel condensation of the core dialdehyde with CH_2 -acidic electron-deficient compounds (3-ethylrhodanine or nitrofluorenes, Scheme 1). Standard nitrating conditions readily introduce 2–4 nitro groups to the 2-, 4-, 5- and 7-positions of the fluorene precursors, enabling a synthetic control over their electron-deficiency (Scheme S1). These nitro groups also enhance the acidity of the methylene protons, making nitrofluorenes ideal for Knoevenagel condensation under mild conditions (pyridine/acetic acid, pyridine or DMF depending on the number of nitro groups) with up to 96% yield. Initial targets were synthesized with an IDTB core and their properties were compared to the previously reported **O-IDTBR**.²⁹ Subsequently, placement of furan in between benzothiadiazole and the acceptor terminus (IDTBF series) was explored to relieve their steric hindrance and enhance backbone planarity. This incorporation of furan was achieved through sequential palladium catalyzed Suzuki coupling of 4,7-dibromobenzothiadiazole with boron-functionalized furan and indacenodithiophene precursors (Scheme S1). The presence of furan in nitrofluorene NFAs results in significantly more planar backbone (discussed later) but also much lower solubility (only mitigated with long hexadecyl and 2-octyldodecyl side chains). In addition, **IT-TNFC₄** with an indacenodithienothiophene (IT) donor core was also synthesized for this study.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the target NFAs.

Optical and Electronic Properties

UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra of the NFAs in dichloromethane (DCM) solution show a broad ICT band ($E_g = 1.7\text{--}1.4$ eV) with comparable extinction coefficients ($\sim 0.8\text{--}1.0 \times 10^5$ M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). This band is red-shifted upon increasing the number of nitro groups on the nitrofluorene acceptor (Figure 1a and Table 1). The optical energy gap of the NFAs is further reduced upon incorporation of furan linkers. Compared to solutions, absorption bands in the solid state are further red-shifted and extend to ~ 1000 nm ($E_g = 1.25$ eV) for the tetranitro derivatives (Figure 1b). While the solid-state absorption bands are broad and featureless for nitrofluorene NFAs with an IDTB core (**IDTB-DNFC₄**, **IDTB-TNFC₄** and **IDTB-TeNF**), clear vibronic splitting was observed in the presence of furan linkers (**IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** and **IDTBF-TeNF**) or with IT as the donor core (**IT-TNFC₄**). This is associated with the difference in molecular planarity, as supported by DFT and NMR (discussed below). All nitrofluorene NFAs are non-emissive as commonly observed for nitroaromatics, likely due to efficient intersystem crossing (ISC) and rotational relaxation induced

by the nitro groups.⁵⁰

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of all studied NFAs showed ~~two~~ reversible oxidation waves (Figure 1c and Table S1, ESI†). While quasi-reversible reduction was observed with **O-IDTBR** at 0.1 V/s, at this scan rate the reduction of all other NFAs was electrochemically irreversible as is commonly seen among similar A–D–A acceptors (e.g. ITIC).¹⁹ The electrochemically determined HOMO levels are significantly raised upon the incorporation of furan moiety by ~0.1 eV (*cf.* IDTBF *vs.* IDTB series, Table 1), but is less sensitive to the change of the acceptor unit. Also, the replacement of IDTB core by IT significantly stabilizes the HOMO (*cf.* **IT-TNFC₄** *vs.* **IDTB-TNFC₄**, Table 1). In contrast, the LUMO levels of the NFAs strongly depend on the electron-deficiency of the acceptor unit where each additional nitro group leads to 200–300 meV lower LUMO levels. While (butoxycarbonyl)dinitrofluorene show similar electron-affinity to rhodanine (LUMO of **IDTB-DNFC₄** at –3.53 eV *vs.* **O-IDTBR** at –3.52 eV), tetranitrofluorene as the acceptor end group (**IDTB-TeNF**, –4.04 eV) results in a dramatic 0.5 eV stabilization of the LUMO compared to rhodanine. Generally, the trend in the frontier orbital levels agreed well with DFT calculations (Figure 1d). Excellent correlation was observed between the DFT-calculated and experimental (CV) LUMO energy levels for all studied NFAs (Figure S1a, ESI†). However, two closely-spaced linear correlations were observed for the HOMO energy levels of IDTB and IDTBF series, with significant deviation for **IT-TNFC₄** (Figure S1b, ESI†). This explains the poor correlation between the computed and experimental HOMO-LUMO gaps for the whole set of acceptors (Figure S1c, ESI†).

Figure 1. (a) Normalized UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra in DCM and (b) in thin films. (c) Cyclic voltammograms in DCM (except **IDTBF-TeNF** in PhCN) containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at the scan rate of 0.1 V s⁻¹. The oxidation waves at 0 V are from ferrocene (Fc) added as an internal standard. (d) DFT: B3LYP/6-31G(d) (dark shaded) and electrochemical (light shaded) frontier molecular orbital energy levels for the studied NFAs. Electrochemical orbital energy levels of PBDB-T are taken from literature.⁵¹

Table 1. Optical, electrochemical and DFT characterizations of the studied NFAs.

	Optical			Electrochemical ^c			DFT: B3LYP/6-31G(d)			
	$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{abs}}$ (nm) ^a	E_g^{opt} (eV) ^a	$E_g^{\text{opt(s)}}$ (eV) ^b	$E_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{CV}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{LUMO}}^{\text{CV}}$ (eV)	E_g^{CV} (eV)	$E_{\text{HOMO}}^{\text{DFT}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{LUMO}}^{\text{DFT}}$ (eV)	E_g^{DFT} (eV)	λ_e (eV) ^d
O-IDTBR	644	1.71	1.60	-5.25	-3.52	1.73	-5.22	-3.34	1.88	0.175
IDTB-DNFC₄	627	1.70	1.55	-5.24	-3.53	1.72	-5.26	-3.32	1.95	0.239
IDTB-TNFC₄	663	1.58	1.43	-5.28	-3.84	1.44	-5.49	-3.61	1.88	0.229
IDTB-TeNF	699	1.48	1.27	-5.30	-4.04	1.27	-5.69	-3.88	1.81	0.204
IDTBF-R	642	1.74	1.68	-5.16	-3.42	1.76	-5.02	-3.15	1.87	0.150
IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂	696	1.53	1.40	-5.18	-3.77	1.41	-5.19	-3.55	1.64	0.107
IDTBF-TeNF	728	1.43	1.25	-5.21	-3.96	1.25	-5.36	-3.81	1.55	0.103
IT-TNFC₄	639	1.74	1.61	-5.48	-3.80	1.67	-5.55	-3.53	2.03	0.163

a) in DCM solutions; b) in thin films drop-cast from PhCN solution for **IDTBF-TeNF** and spin-coated from PhCl solutions for other NFAs; E_g derived from absorption onsets; c) CVs were performed in PhCN for **IDTBF-TeNF** and in DCM for other NFAs; orbital energies were calculated as $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -4.8 \text{ eV} - e \cdot E_{\text{ox}}^{1/2}$ and $E_{\text{LUMO}} = -4.8 \text{ eV} - e \cdot E_{\text{red}}^{\text{onset}}$ (vs. Fc/Fc⁺, Table S1, ESI[†]); d) internal reorganization energy for electron transfer, calculated according to the common four-point adiabatic formalism: $\lambda_e = (E_0^{-1} - E_0^0) + (E_{-1}^0 - E_{-1}^{-1})$, where E_0 and E_{-1} denote the energies at

geometries optimized for the neutral and negatively charged species, respectively, and the superscripts refer to the charge of the species.

Planarity

It was previously shown that the planarity of conjugated molecules can be evaluated by extracting the planarity index $\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle$ from the rotational population distribution of the dihedral angle φ over the bridging C–C bonds.⁵² Most of the known efficient A–D–A NFAs have a highly planar backbone with $\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle > 0.9$ between the donor core and the acceptor termini.⁵² To examine the compatibility of nitrofluorenes with commonly used donors, DFT dihedral scans were performed over the bridging C–C bond between various donor-acceptor dyads (Figure 2) and $\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle$ was calculated. While highly planar backbone can be obtained by bridging benzothiadiazole with rhodanine (lowest-energy dihedral angle, $\varphi^* = 0^\circ$), using dinitrofluorene as the acceptor induces a significant twist ($\varphi^* = 45^\circ$) and is expected to be detrimental. However, furan as the donor results in much higher planarity ($\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle = 0.962$) compared to thiophene ($\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle = 0.804$) and especially benzothiadiazole ($\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle = 0.448$). This is due to the less steric hindrance of furan and secondary interaction between oxygen and the adjacent fluorene hydrogen. Enhanced planarity of the conjugated backbone is our main premise behind the use of furan to bridge nitrofluorenes in the IDTBF design. This planarity is experimentally supported by NMR showing a significantly down-shifted proton at the 2-position of the nitrofluorene end-group for **IDTBF-TeNF** (10.45 ppm) compared to **IDTB-TeNF** (~9.2 ppm), indicative of the former proton residing in the deshielding region of the aromatic furan ring. The presence of furan linkers also results in significantly lower reorganization energy (0.103 eV for **IDTBF-TeNF** vs. 0.204 eV for **IDTB-TeNF**), which is also among the lowest reported up to date for NFAs.⁵³

Figure 2. DFT probability density ($T = 298$ K) as a function of the dihedral angle for the bridging C–C bond of different donor-acceptor dyads labeled with $\langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle$.

Solid-State Packing

Single crystals of **IDTB-TeNF** and **IDTBF-R** were grown by slow diffusion of acetone vapor into a solution of the NFA in chloroform or toluene. Single crystal X-ray diffraction (XRD) reveals a 2D brickwork packing for **IDTB-TeNF** with two (half-)molecules in the asymmetric unit (green/red), in contrast to **O-IDTBR** and **IDTBF-R** forming 3D reticular networks (Figure 3). The dihedral angle between IDT and benzothiadiazole units is $<10^{\circ}$, while large twists of $\sim 38^{\circ}$ were observed with the nitrofluorene termini, in line with DFT calculations (2° and 36° , respectively). Electronic couplings $|J|$ of 15–30 meV for LUMO was calculated along the π -stack of the nitrofluorene acceptors, suggesting good electron transfer through the 2D network. However, efficient charge propagation is likely hampered by the lack of charge percolation channel along the third direction.

Figure 3. Single crystal structure of **IDTB-TeNF** (CCDC 2223485), **O-IDTBR**³¹ and **IDTBF-R** (CCDC 2223487): molecular geometry (top) labeled with dihedral angles, top-down view (middle) and side view (bottom) labeled with electronic coupling $|J|$ along the π - π stacking calculated using Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF). Molecules in light and dark green represent neighbors with identical geometry, whereas molecules in red have a different geometry. Hydrogens and some side chains were omitted to reduce clutter.

Device Studies

BHJ solar cells were fabricated with an inverted configuration (glass/ITO/ZnO/blend/MoO₃/Ag) to elucidate the structure-property-performance relationships and demonstrate their application in OPVs (Figure 4 and Table 2). Commercially available PBDB-T was employed as the electron-donor polymer as it offers complementary optical absorption and energetics matching the NFAs investigated in this study. The reference devices (PBDB-T:**O-IDTBR**) exhibited an average PCE of 8.5%, slightly higher than previously reported results ($\sim 7.5\%$).⁵⁴ The nitrofluorene NFAs showed inferior OPV performance in comparison to **O-IDTBR** owing to the combined effect of lower open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) and fill factor (FF). **IDTB-TNFC**₄ based devices yielded the highest PCE of 4.5% amongst IDTB-nitrofluorenes NFAs. Space-charge limited current (SCLC, Figure S2, ESI†) measurements revealed more than an order of magnitude lower electron mobility for **IDTB-TNFC**₄ ($1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) films as compared to **O-IDTBR** ($3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The inefficient electron transport in the BHJ leads to pronounced charge recombination, resulting in lower J_{SC} values. Moreover, the low electron mobility in the blend would also contribute to an imbalance in hole and electron transport leading to low FF values. The inferior OPV performance metrics for IDTB-nitrofluorene NFAs are not too surprising given their

twisted backbone and unfavorable molecular packing as discussed earlier. The backbone planarization in furan-bridged **IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** leads to lower calculated reorganization energy for electron transfer and higher measured electron mobility ($8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) which explains the slightly higher FF. The furan bridge also results in ~ 0.1 eV higher LUMO (Table 1) which aided in achieving a superior V_{OC} (0.85 V) compared to its non-bridged counterpart (**IDTB-TNFC₄**, $V_{\text{OC}} = 0.79$ V). However, the unexpectedly lower J_{SC} of the furan-bridged **IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** compared to the non-bridged **IDTB-TNFC₄** resulted in the same modest PCE of $\sim 4\%$. We note that despite the long alkyl chains **IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** still shows lower solubility compared to other NFAs and this might also be detrimental for its device performance.

Table 2. Photovoltaic performance of glass/ITO/ZnO/blend/MoO_x/Ag solar cells with a 1:1 blend of PBDB-T and different NFAs.

	V_{OC} / V	$J_{\text{SC}} / \text{mA cm}^{-2}$	FF / %	PCE / % average (highest)
O-IDTBR	0.96 ± 0.01	14.6 ± 0.3	61 ± 3	8.5 ± 0.5 (8.9)
IDTB-DNFC₄	0.93 ± 0.02	7.1 ± 0.3	35 ± 3	2.3 ± 0.3 (2.7)
IDTB-TNFC₄	0.79 ± 0.01	12.6 ± 0.5	43 ± 1	4.3 ± 0.2 (4.5)
IDTB-TeNF	0.56 ± 0.01	4.5 ± 0.7	31 ± 4	0.8 ± 0.2 (1.1)
IDTBF-R	0.72 ± 0.02	2.3 ± 0.1	41 ± 1	0.7 ± 0.1 (0.7)
IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂	0.85 ± 0.01	9.1 ± 0.4	49 ± 2	3.8 ± 0.2 (4.0)
IT-TNFC₄	0.80 ± 0.04	8.2 ± 1.5	25 ± 2	1.7 ± 0.4 (2.4)

Figure 4. Structure of PBDB-T donor polymer used in BHJ cells and J - V curves of glass/ITO/ZnO/blend/MoO_x/Ag cells with a 1:1 blend of PBDB-T and different NFAs.

Film Morphology

Grazing incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) was employed to assess the microstructure of the blend films of the NFAs. The 2D GIWAXS patterns of pristine PBDB-T and its blend with the NFAs are presented in Figure 5 (the corresponding out-of-plane and in-plane line cuts are shown in Figure S3). The pristine PBDB-T film exhibits an out-of-plane (100) lamellar reflection ($q_z = 0.31 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) corresponding to the lamellar packing ($d_{100} = 2.0 \text{ nm}$) of the alkylated polymer chains. The PBDB-T:**O-IDTBR** blend displays the same peak as well as an additional peak at $q = 0.45 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ which corresponds well to the $d_{011} = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ reflection of **O-IDTBR** (as expected based on its single crystal structure³¹). However, the PBDB-T:**IDTB-TNFC₄** blend does not show any additional features beyond the (100) peak of PBDB-T. Notably, no scattering signatures is observed for PBDB-T:**IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** blend films. This suppression of the film crystallinity for nitrofluorene-based NFAs compared to the **O-IDTBR** reference could be a result of their excessive miscibility with PBDB-T, possibly due to long alkyl chains on the nitrofluorene termini (required

for solubility). Such behavior is detrimental for charge transport and is likely one of the reasons for the low measured J_{sc} and FF.

Figure 5. 2D GIWAXS patterns of (annealed) PBDB-T and its blends with **O-IDTBR**, **IDTB-TNFC₄** and **IDTB-TNFC₈C₁₂**.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images show similar surface topography of all studied BHJ films with root-mean-square (RMS) roughness of 3–4 nm (Figure 6). Qualitatively, more uniform domains and sharper grain boundaries were observed for the **O-IDTBR** blend, which agrees with the highest crystallinity of this film observed by GIWAXS. However, the comparison between different nitrofluorene NFA blends reveals no clear correlation with the corresponding device performance. Scanning transmission electron microscopy imaging was performed for **O-IDTBR**, **IDTB-TNFC₄** and **IDTB-TNFC₈C₁₂** blends and revealed a distinct phase separation in all cases, with a coarsened morphology in the latter blend, similar to that observed in AFM (Figure S4, ESI†).

Figure 6. AFM images ($3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}$) of the studied BHJ blends.

Conclusion

Two series (**IDTB-NF** and **IDTBF-NF**) of A–D–A push-pull type electron acceptors with indacenodithiophene donor core (D) and nitrofluorene termini (A) have been synthesized and used as non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs) for bulk heterojunction solar cells. The variation of the structure of the nitrofluorene termini allowed tuning their HOMO and LUMO energies and achieving narrower energy gaps compared to reference acceptors **O-IDTBR** and **IDTBF-R** with rhodamine termini. Intramolecular charge transfer in these NFAs results in strong and very broad absorption in the visible and near-infrared region of the spectrum (up to 900 nm), with the optical energy gaps E_g^{opt} of $\sim 1.55\text{--}1.25$ eV. Incorporation of furan between the D and A moieties (**IDTBF-NF** vs. **IDTB-NF** series) raised the HOMO energy levels by ca. 70–100 meV, but weakly affected E_g . The planarity of these compounds was evaluated by DFT using planarity index $\langle \cos^2\varphi \rangle$ from the rotational population distribution, showing significant variations with the structures. Single crystal analysis confirmed a much larger twist of nitrofluorene end groups in **IDTB-TeNF** ($\sim 38^\circ$) compared to rhodamine end groups in **O-IDTBR** ($\sim 8^\circ$). While **O-IDTBR** (and most other high-performing NFAs) show 3D interpenetrating network of π -interactions, a 2D brickwork packing was observed for **IDTB-TeNF**. The blends of **IDTB-NF** and **IDTBF-NF** electron acceptors with PBDB-T polymer donor have been tested in bulk heterojunction solar cells. The structure of the nitrofluorene termini significantly affects the device performance, and highest PCEs were achieved with **IDTB-TNFC₄** and **IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂** acceptors having long-chain

solubilizing ester groups (4.5% and 4.0%, respectively). These values are lower than that for **O-IDTBR** (8.5%), but higher than for furan-extended **IDTBF-R** reference (0.7%). These studies show the potential of nitroaromatics (and more specifically nitrofluorenes) as electron-withdrawing building blocks for the design of novel π -electron acceptors and donor-acceptor systems for organic electronics. However, further optimization of the molecular packing and film morphology is required to improve their performance in OPVs.

Experimental

Device Fabrications & Measurements. Patterned ITO substrates were sonicated sequentially in deionized water with detergent, acetone and isopropanol for 10 min each, dried with a stream of nitrogen and treated with oxygen plasma for 10 min. ZnO layer was deposited by spin-coating a solution of Zn(OAc)₂·2H₂O (0.2 g/mL) in 2-methoxyethanol (containing 3% ethanolamine) at 4000 rpm for 30 s in air followed by thermal annealing at 150 °C for 45 min. PBDB-T and the NFAs were dissolved separately in chlorobenzene (20 mg/mL), stirred at 60 °C for 12 h, mixed (1:1 v/v), stirred at 60 °C for 45 min, spin-coated at 2000 rpm for 45 s and annealed at 130 °C for 10 min. MoO_x (10 nm) and Ag (100 nm) layers were deposited by thermal evaporation through a shadow mask under $\sim 3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar, yielding a device area of 6 mm². Current density-voltage (J - V) characteristics were measured at room temperature under inert glove-box environment using an LED solar simulator (LSH-7320) at AM1.5 solar illumination calibrated to a silicon reference cell with a Keithley 2400 source meter.

Synthesis of IDTB-DNFC₄: To a solution of **IDTB-2CHO** (0.075 g, 0.072 mmol) and **DNFC₄** (0.098 g, 0.275 mmol) in 9 mL PhMe was added 0.48 mL AcOH and 0.62 mL pyridine and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone and purified by column chromatography (CHCl₃), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a dark purplish solid (0.069 g, 56%). The product is a 3:2 mixture of *E/Z* isomers over the vinylene bridge. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 9.04 (d, 1.2H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 9.00 (d, 0.8H, $J = 2.2$ Hz), 8.94 (d, 1.2H, $J = 2.2$ Hz), 8.91 (d, 0.8H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.81 (d, 1.2H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.77 (d, 1.2H, $J = 8.8$ Hz), 8.72 (d, 0.8H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.69 (d, 0.8H, $J = 8.8$ Hz), 8.59 (s, 0.8H), 8.58 (s, 1.2H), 8.36 (dd, 0.8H, $J = 8.8$ Hz, $J' = 2.2$ Hz), 8.30 (dd, 1.2H, $J = 8.8$ Hz, $J' = 2.2$ Hz),

8.26 (s, 2H), 8.20 (d, 1.2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 8.13–8.07 (m, 2.8H), 7.46 (s, 2H), 4.55 (m, 4H), 2.19–1.97 (m, 8H), 1.89 (m, 4H), 1.56 (m, 4H), 1.23–1.12 (m, 40H), 1.08–0.87 (m, 14H), 0.80 (t, 12H, $J = 6.9$ Hz). APCI-HRMS (m/z): calculated 1715.6886 for $[\text{C}_{98}\text{H}_{106}\text{N}_8\text{O}_{12}\text{S}_4+\text{H}]^+$, found 1715.6882 (–0.23 ppm).

Synthesis of IDTB-TNFC₄: **IDTB-2CHO** (0.075 g, 0.072 mmol) and **TNFC₄** (0.087 g, 0.217 mmol) were stirred overnight in a mixture of 10 mL DMF and 5 mL CHCl_3 at room temperature. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone and purified by column chromatography (CHCl_3), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a purplish black solid (0.105 g, 81%). The product is a 2:1 mixture of *E/Z* isomers over the vinylene bridge. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 9.14 (d, 0.67H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 9.09 (d, 1.33H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 9.07 (d, 1.33H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 9.06 (d, 0.67H, $J = 2.2$ Hz), 8.89 (d, 0.67H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.81 (d, 1.33H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.77–8.74 (m, 3.33H), 8.70 (d, 0.67H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.30 (s, 2H), 8.19 (d, 0.67H, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 8.15–8.10 (m, 3.33H), 7.48 (s, 2H), 4.41 (m, 4H), 2.20–1.97 (m, 8H), 1.84 (m, 4H), 1.53 (m, 4H), 1.23–1.12 (m, 40H), 1.06–0.88 (m, 14H), 0.79 (t, 12H, $J = 6.9$ Hz). APCI-HRMS (m/z): calculated 1805.6587 for $[\text{C}_{98}\text{H}_{104}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_{16}\text{S}_4+\text{H}]^+$, found 1805.6574 (–0.72 ppm).

Synthesis of IDTB-TeNF: **IDTB-2CHO** (0.071 g, 0.068 mmol) and **TeNF** (0.166 g, 0.479 mmol) were stirred for 3 h in a mixture of 10 mL DMF and 5 mL CHCl_3 at room temperature. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was washed with acetone and purified by column chromatography (CH_2Cl_2), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a purplish black solid (0.102 g, 88%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 9.21 (d, 2H, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 9.16 (d, 2H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.96 (d, 2H, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 8.90 (s, 2H), 8.88 (d, 2H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.34 (s, 2H), 8.19 (d, 2H, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 8.14 (d, 2H, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 7.52 (s, 2H), 2.21–1.98 (m, 8H), 1.24–1.10 (m, 40H), 1.06–0.88 (m, 8H), 0.80 (t, 12H, $J = 6.9$ Hz). APCI-HRMS (m/z): calculated 1695.5240 for $[\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{86}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{16}\text{S}_4+\text{H}]^+$, found 1695.5232 (–0.47 ppm). Crystal structure: CCDC 2223485.

Synthesis of IDTBF-R: To a solution of **IDTBF-2CHO** (0.050 g, 0.031 mmol) and 3-ethylrhodanine (0.050 g, 0.31 mmol) in 4.5 mL PhMe was added 0.5 mL AcOH. The mixture was refluxed for 24 h under nitrogen. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone, purified by column chromatography (CHCl_3), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a wine red solid (0.056 g, 95%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 8.22 (d, 2H, $J = 7.7$ Hz), 8.21 (s, 2H), 8.12 (d, 2H, $J = 7.7$ Hz), 7.94 (d, 2H, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 7.56 (s, 2H), 7.44 (s, 2H), 7.11 (d, 2H, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 4.25 (q, 4H, $J = 7.1$ Hz), 2.17–1.94 (m, 8H), 1.34 (t, 6H, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 1.27–1.09 (m,

104H), 1.06–0.86 (m, 8H), 0.84 (t, 12H, $J = 7.0$ Hz). APCI-HRMS (m/z): calculated 1906.0027 for $[\text{C}_{112}\text{H}_{156}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}_8+\text{H}]^+$, found 1906.0001 (–1.36 ppm). Crystal structure: CCDC 2223487.

Synthesis of IDTBF-TNFC₈C₁₂: To a solution of **IDTBF-2CHO** (0.065 g, 0.040 mmol) and **TNFC₈C₁₂** (0.100 g, 0.160 mmol) in 8 mL PhMe was added 0.4 mL pyridine. The mixture was refluxed overnight under nitrogen. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone, purified by column chromatography (CHCl_3), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a bluish black solid (0.109 g, 96%). The product is a 1:1 mixture of *E/Z* isomers over the vinylene bridge. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 10.37 (d, 1H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 10.30 (d, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 9.01 (d, 1H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.96 (d, 1H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.94 (d, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.83 (d, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.82–8.78 (m, 2H), 8.75 (d, 1H, $J = 7.8$ Hz), 8.67 (d, 1H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.26–8.16 (m, 6H), 7.79 (s, 1H), 7.76 (s, 1H), 7.50–7.47 (m, 2H), 7.46 (s, 2H), 4.32 (t, 4H, $J = 5.5$ Hz), 2.20–1.97 (m, 8H), 1.94–1.84 (m, 2H), 1.50–1.10 (m, 168H), 1.07–0.85 (m, 20H), 0.82 (t, 12H, $J = 7.0$ Hz). APCI-HRMS (m/z): calculated 2834.6815 for $[\text{C}_{170}\text{H}_{236}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_{18}\text{S}_4+\text{H}]^+$, found 2834.6868 (+1.87 ppm).

Synthesis of IDTBF-TeNF: To a solution of **IDTBF-2CHO** (0.030 g, 0.019 mmol) and **TeNF** (0.036 g, 0.099 mmol) in 5 mL PhMe was added 0.1 mL pyridine and the mixture was stirred overnight. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone, purified by column chromatography (CHCl_3), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a bluish black solid (0.039 g, 93%). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 10.45 (d, 2H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 9.10 (d, 2H, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 9.03 (d, 2H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.88 (d, 2H, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 2.19–1.98 (m, 8H), 1.27–1.10 (m, 104H), 1.05–0.86 (m, 8H), 0.82 (t, 12H, $J = 7.0$ Hz). MALDI-MS (m/z): calculated 2276.05 for $[\text{C}_{128}\text{H}_{154}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{18}\text{S}_4+\text{H}]^+$, found 2276.27.

Synthesis of IT-TNFC₄: To a solution of **IT-2CHO** (0.045 g, 0.042 mmol) and **TNFC₄** (0.060 g, 0.150 mmol) in 5 mL PhMe was added 0.2 mL pyridine. The mixture was refluxed overnight under nitrogen. The solvent was evaporated, and the residue was washed with acetone, purified by column chromatography (CHCl_3), concentrated and precipitated with MeOH to give a bluish black solid (0.063 g, 82%). The product is a 3:1 mixture of *E/Z* isomers over the vinylene bridge. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm) 9.80 (d, 1.5H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 9.73 (d, 0.5H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.93 (d, 0.5H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.86 (d, 1.5H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.82 (d, 1.5H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.80 (d, 0.5H, $J = 1.9$ Hz), 8.71 (d, 0.5H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.67 (d, 1.5H, $J = 2.0$ Hz), 8.20 (s, 1.5H), 8.17 (s, 0.5H), 7.96 (s, 0.5H), 7.93 (s, 1.5H), 7.66 (s, 2H), 7.22 (d, 8H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 7.18 (d, 8H, $J = 8.5$ Hz), 4.39 (t, 4H, $J = 6.8$ Hz), 2.59

(t, 8H, $J = 7.9$ Hz), 1.82 (quint, 4H, $J = 7.2$ Hz), 1.60 (quint, 8H, $J = 7.6$ Hz), 1.51 (m, 4H), 1.37–1.24 (m, 24H), 1.02 (t, 6H, $J = 7.4$ Hz), 0.85 (t, 12H, $J = 6.9$ Hz). ESI-MS (m/z): calculated 1863.60 for $[\text{C}_{106}\text{H}_{100}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{16}\text{S}_4+\text{Na}]^+$, found 1863.61.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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